

USE OF ICT IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF UNSATURATED CARBOHYDRATES

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Anotatsiya O'quv jarayonini o'quvchilarning Integral ta'lim texnologiyasi. takroriy takrorlash, muammoli ta'lim texnologiyasi. Kimyoning butun kursi muammoli ta'limni akt orqali samaradorligini oshirish usullari. Talabalarning qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan yangi, texnologiyalardan foydalanish. Talabanning ta'lim jarayonining faol ishtirokchisiga aylanishini ta'minlash. Kimyo darslaridagi to'yinmagan uglevodorodlar mavzusida ma'ruza va laboratoriyalarda qo'llayotgan innovatsion texnologiyalarni akt ga bog'lab ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish.

Kalit so'zlar: Tayanch so'zlar: muammoli vaziyatni bayon qilish, muammoli masala, kimyodan didaktik birliklarni kengaytirish, "Uglevodorodlar" mavzusida ko'p bosqichli texnologiyalari.

Аннотация: Интегральная образовательная технология образовательного процесса студентов. повторение, проблемная технология обучения. Методы повышения эффективности проблемного обучения через весь курс химии. Использование новых технологий, направленных на развитие способностей учащихся. Обеспечить, чтобы студент стал активным участником образовательного процесса. Повышение эффективности обучения за счет подключения инновационных технологий, используемых в лекциях и лабораторных работах по теме непредельных углеводородов на уроках химии.

Ключевые слова: Ключевые слова: описание проблемной ситуации, проблемная задача, расширение дидактических единиц из химии, многоуровневые технологии по теме «Углеводороды»

Annotation Integral educational technology of students of the educational process. repetition, problem-based learning technology. Methods of increasing the effectiveness of problem-based learning through the whole course of chemistry. Using new technologies aimed at developing students' abilities. To ensure that the student becomes an active participant in the educational process. Improving the effectiveness of education by connecting innovative technologies used in lectures and laboratories on the topic of unsaturated hydrocarbons in chemistry classes.

Key words: Key words: description of the problem situation, problem problem, expansion of didactic units from chemistry, multi-level technologies on the topic "Hydrocarbons".

The modern educational process cannot be imagined without the search for new, more effective technologies aimed at developing students' creative abilities. To ensure that students become active participants in the educational process, and the teacher is the organizer of the student's cognitive activity. Innovative technologies used in their laboratories are presented in chemistry classes. The use of modern technologies in the teaching of chemistry, the use of integrated educational technology, helps students to improve their academic performance.

Integral educational technology. repeated repetitions, mandatory step-by-step control, high level of difficulty. This technology is used in the study of chemistry in high school. These are active forms. training: classes - lectures, seminars, practical exercises, consultations. Theoretical material is presented in "block". A two-way explanation is used: first in the form of a lecture with a demonstration and the use of visual aids, then briefly, highlighting the main knowledge, highlighting the most important of the above. new material, learned in a lecture, is repeated by students again and again and considered in various connections seminar classes. The main directions of work in the seminar are determined by the motto. For example: "Experience is the basis of knowledge", "Analysis is given to the structure and its properties", "Everything is known. in comparison", "Practice is the criterion of truth" and so on. Lectures are introductory, current, final. your idea of spending on building skills, discussing what has been learned, teaching students to express, evaluate the content of the material. The lecture is conducted deductively or inductively, depending on the preparation of the lesson. An inductive lecture develops students' mental abilities, the ability to formulate hypotheses and generalize.

It is possible to conduct a problem presentation for self-explanation of the issues that students are involved in lectures, to activate mental activity, in the process of forming their thinking ability to solve the tasks assigned to them.

We try to make every lecture challenging. First, a problem is posed and students are led to a solution to that problem. For example: lecture on "Aromatic hydrocarbons". Based on the structural cyclic formula of benzene proposed by Kekule, the name of which is characteristic of a certain substance, the reactions of benzene with bromine water and potassium permanganate. Benzene does not react with them. A problematic situation was created in front of the students. A contrast is shown between the structure (Kekule formula) and properties of the molecule. The educational lecture of students in lecture classes is a very important, active form of

work on the development of student thinking. Students are advised to make notes, diagrams, support systems, blocks on the topic.

Problem-based educational technology. The entire chemistry course involves problem-based learning. All organic chemistry lectures are problematic. The study of general and inorganic chemistry is carried out together with the lesson, problem situations, questions, and the use of the act will allow them to easily find and find answers to difficult questions. Today, conducting lessons using information technologies in education helps both the teacher and the student to develop in the field of education. Problem situations in lessons on other topics, departments, similar questions, ways to solve the problem can be searched.

Multi-level educational technology can also be used to teach unsaturated carbohydrates in the classroom. It is impossible to effectively organize the educational process without applying an individualized approach to students according to their inclinations, interests and capabilities. Differentiation is of particular importance in teaching chemistry. This is due to the specificity of the subject: For some students, mastering chemistry is associated with significant difficulties, while others demonstrate the ability to learn this subject. The problem can be solved by the technology of level differentiation of the strength of knowledge in chemistry. To do this, we define the following sequence of actions: choose the level of difficulty suitable for students; Determining the content of the educational material; Developing a technological map for students;

by monitoring and assessing student learning, ensuring that assessment reflects learning, not just learning;

to explain to the students the technologies of achieving the illumination of the topic using the act.

A lecture or a laboratory on the topic of unsaturated hydrocarbons, which method or act is used to teach students, will increase their interest in learning the subject by creating new methods and using the act. We should not forget that the study of each subject requires an important task, not the teacher or the school, but the student's knowledge development.

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